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Susceptibility of genotypes/varieties of pigeonpea to *euchrysops cnejus fabricius*

J.C. Prajapati and Bindu Panickar

Centre of Excellence for Research on Pulses,

Sardarkrushinagar Dantiwada Agricultural University, Sardarkrushinagar, Distt. Banaskantha, Gujarat 385 506

Amongst the different colour of flower, *E. cnejus* preferred yellow colour (av. no. 1.41 eggs/plant) for egg laying viz., GT-1, GT-101, UPAS-120, PAU-881, SKNP-207, SKNP-224, SKNP-0610, SKNP-0615, AL-201, AL-1495, AL-1735, AL-1747, BP-06-38 and BP-06-42. However, red colour flower Vaishali was least (av. no. 1.19 eggs/plant) preferred for egg laying. GT-1 had significantly lowest egg population and was at par with GT-101, UPAS-120, SKNP-0610, SKNP-0615 and SKNP-207. UPAS-120 corded significantly less larval population than rest of varieties/genotypes. GT-1 had green with brown streaks on pods with maximum (av. no. 1.02 larvae per plant) population. Green pods were observed only in GT-1 with an average number of 0.75 larvae per plant). Minimum pod damage (2.18%) was noticed in green pods. Whereas, maximum pod damage (6.64%) was noticed in pods having green with brown streak. Higher pod damage by *E. cnejus* was noticed in DT (8.34%) as compared to NDT (5.34%) genotypes or varieties of pigeonpea. Fourteen genotypes or varieties were white seeded with maximum pod damage (6.51%) while the red colour seeds in UPAS-120 had less (3.94%).

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Screening of watermelon [*Citrullus lanatus* (Thunb.) Mansf.] varieties/ genotypes against fruit fly (*Bactrocera cucurbitae* (Coquillett)) in hot arid region of Rajasthan

Shravan M. Haldhar, B.R. Choudhary, R. Bhargava and S.K. Sharma

Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, Beechwal, Bikaner 334 006

Host plant resistance is an important component for management of the melon fruit fly, *Bactrocera cucurbitae* (Coquillett) owing to difficulties associated with its chemical and biological control. The twenty seven watermelon varieties/ genotypes were taken for screening against melon fruit fly. The significant differences were found in per centage fruit infestation and larval density per fruit among the tested varieties/ genotypes during screening. The larval density per fruit had a significant positive correlation with per centage fruit infestation. Watermelon varieties/ genotypes viz., RSS-1, AHW/BR-18, AHW/BR-8, AHW/BR-21, AHW/BR-20, AHW/YF-4, AHW/BR-19, AHW/BR-96, AHW/YF-5, AHW/YF-7, AHW/BR-10, RW-187-2, AHW/BR-137, Durgapura Lal, AHW/BR-9, Sugar Baby, AHW-65, AHW-19, IC 582909, BSM-1, AHW/BR-16, Charleston Grey, Asahi Yamato, Arka Manik, AHW/BR-60, AHW/BR-12 and Thar Manak were evaluated to screen out the suitable resistant/susceptible varieties/ genotypes against the fruit fly in hot arid region of Rajasthan. The results imparted that the percentage of fruit infestation and larval population per fruit on tested varieties/ genotypes of watermelon varied significantly. Pooled data showed that the AHW/BR-60, BSM-1, IC 582909, AHW/BR-9, AHW/BR-137, RW-187-2, AHW/BR-10, AHW/BR-18, AHW/BR-8, AHW/BR-21, AHW/BR-20 and AHW/YF-4 were categorized as susceptible varieties/ genotypes with fruit infestation (55.72%, 59.28%, 53.05%, 67.20%, 60.43%, 61.83%, 63.87%, 63.62%, 59.45%, 59.62%, 62.52% and 55.68%, respectively) and larval population per fruit (17.12, 17.85, 16.45, 19.23, 17.90, 18.48, 18.38, 18.32, 18.40, 17.57, 17.93 and 17.70, respectively). Whereas, the varieties/ genotypes Asahi Yamato, AHW/BR-16 and Thar Manak had fruit infestation (12.75%, 15.05% and 18.18%, respectively) and larval population per plant (10.13, 10.82 and 11.08, respectively) and declared as

resistant varieties/ genotypes to fruit fly. Lower values of host plant susceptibility indices based on fruit infestation (HPSI) were recorded on resistant varieties/ genotypes, Asahi Yamato, AHW/BR-16 and Thar Manak (28.85%, 34.05% and 41.14%, respectively) could be used as a source of resistance for developing watermelon varieties genotypes resistant to fruit fly.

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Susceptibility in brinjal varieties against shoot and fruit borer, *Leucinodus orbonalis* Guen.

R.G. Samota and B.L. Jat

Department of Entomology, SKNCOA, Jobner 303 329 (Sri Karan Narendra Agriculture University)

Brinjal, *Solanum melongena* L. belongs to Solanaceae, is an important vegetable crop grown through out the world, especially in South Asia and a native of India. The brinjal crop is attacked by a number of insect-pests right from germination to harvest of the crop. shoot and fruit borer, *L. orbonalis* is one of the major constraint in achieving potential yield and remain active throughout the year with many overlapping generations. Crop losses have been reported to the tune of 20-89 per cent in various parts of country by this pest. The susceptible brinjal varieties were screened against *L. orbonalis* at Horticulture research farm SKNCOA, Jobner. Out of eight varieties of brinjal screened against shoot and fruit borer, *L. orbonalis*, none of the varieties were found completely free from the infestation of pest. Based on the statistical categorization, the varieties Pusa Uttam, Ravaiya and Kavach were found less susceptible having shoot damage below 18.61 per cent and fruit damage both number and weight basis below 44.21 and 39.91 per cent, respectively. Whereas, varieties Pusa Purple Round and Raunak were highly susceptible having shoot damage above 26.51 per cent and fruit damage both on number and weight basis above 59.25 and 55.63 per cent, respectively. The remaining varieties viz., Koyalia, Utkarsh and Krishna proved moderately susceptible having 18.61 to 26.51 per cent shoot damage, 44.21 to 59.25 and 39.91 to 55.63 per cent fruit damage both on number and weight basis, respectively.

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Evaluation of various grain sorghum hybrids for resistance to shoot fly *Atherigona soccata*

V.U. Sonalkar, S.N. Kale, R.B. Ghorade, V.V. Kalpande and Seema Nemade

All Indian Coordinated Sorghum Improvement Project,

Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola 444 104, Maharashtra

Nine sorghum hybrids along with four released hybrids, two resistant and three susceptible national checks and one local resistant check were evaluated for their reaction to shoot fly at Akola during *kharif* 2013. The objectives were to determine the relative resistance of sorghum hybrids to major pest of sorghum and to identify the new insect pest resistant grain sorghum hybrid. The sorghum entries were sown at recommended plant spacing in two rows of 2.0 m each. The shoot fly dead heart damage was recorded at 28 days after emergence by counting total number of plants and number of shoot fly damaged dead hearts in two rows of 2.0 m each entry. In addition to shoot fly damage, plant stand and seedling glossiness score were recorded 12 days after emergence. The seedling glossiness score was ranged from 1.00 for IS 18551 and highest of 4.67 each for SPH 1705, SPH 1731, SPH 12736 CSH-23 and swarna. The highest of 92.43 per cent shoot fly damage was observed in SPH 1736. The lowest dead hearts due to shoot fly were in hybrid SPH-1703 with 67.74 per cent dead hearts which was significantly less than all released hybrids except CSH-25 (80.75 %) indicating the relatively tolerance of hybrid SPH 1703 to shoot fly. Shoot fly damage was positively correlated with seedling glossiness score.